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Novel Direction-of-Arrival-Based Localization in Massive DECT-2020 5G NR Networks

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Abstract—This research investigates an affordable, energy-efficient direction-of-arrival (DOA)-based localization solution for digital enhanced cordless telecommunications (DECTs) 2020 new radio (NR), a new standard lacking a native positioning feature. This standard enables massive Internet of Things (IoT) networks, a vast 5G network interconnecting an unparalleled number of low-cost and battery-operated smart sensors. However, integrating DOA localization into such networks is challenging due to cost constraints and power limitations. We propose a potentially cost-effective solution using a single radio-frequency (RF) chain for uniform L-shaped antenna arrays. Each antenna takes turns sampling the orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) signal via an RF switch, enabled by time-dividing the OFDM signal into sample and switch slots. Further, we introduce a novel DOA method optimized for single Line-of-Sight (LOS) OFDM signals and array sequential sampling. This method leverages the dual shift-invariant properties of L-shaped antenna arrays and the array frequency response to estimate the azimuth and elevation angles. Experiments in an indoor environment reveal that at a signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of 15 dB, over 50% of data achieve subdegree angular accuracy, increasing to 75% at 20 dB. Thus, over 50% of position estimations fall below the submeter error level at 15 dB SNR, rising to nearly 75% at 25 dB SNR. Our findings also indicate that halving the slot rate by proportionately reducing active subcarriers does not compromise accuracy. Experiments on the nRF52480 system-on-chip show the new DOA method is both fast and energy-efficient, taking only 0.76–2.26 ms and consuming 5.08–15.1 nWh.

Index Terms—5G indoor localization, direction of arrival (DOA), massive Internet of Things (IoT), orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) signals.

I. INTRODUCTION

MASSIVE Internet of Things (IoT), also known as massive machine-type communications (mMTCs), deploys

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a vast 5G network interconnecting millions of low-power, battery-operated, and cost-effective smart sensors and actuators [1]. These intelligent devices play a crucial role in monitoring diverse systems, gathering data for cloud-based analysis or local processing, and executing actions based on the analyzed data. A prominent example of massive IoT is the digital enhanced cordless telecommunications (DECTs) 2020 new radio (NR) [2], distinguished as the inaugural noncellular 5G technology adopting a mesh network architecture. DECT-2020 NR is designed for mMTC applications [3] and meets the requirements for ultra reliable low latency communications (URLLCs) and mMTC of the International Mobile Telecommunications-2020 [4]. It has several key advantages over well-known wireless technologies, such as Bluetooth, ZigBee, and LoRa.

DECT-2020 NR, leveraging orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM), can achieve data rates of up to several megabits per second (Mbps), depending on the specific implementation and bandwidth used [5]. In comparison, Bluetooth 5.0 offers data rates up to 2 Mb/s [6], ZigBee typically supports up to 250 kilobits per second (Kb/s) [7], and LoRa is optimized for lower data rates, generally ranging from 0.3 to 50 Kb/s [8].

DECT-2020 NR also provides significantly greater range and coverage, often reaching a few kilometres in outdoor environments, making it ideal for large-scale industrial applications. In contrast, ZigBee and Bluetooth have much shorter ranges, usually within tens of meters, which makes them more suitable for personal area networks or home automation. LoRa, however, excels in long-range communication, achieving up to 15–20 km in rural or open areas, and 2–5 km in urban environments [9].

Operating in its own dedicated 1.9 GHz frequency band, DECT-2020 NR experiences less interference from other systems compared to the crowded ISM bands used by Bluetooth and ZigBee and the sub-GHz frequency band of 400–900 MHz used by LoRa. This results in more reliable communication, especially in environments with numerous wireless devices.

In terms of latency, DECT-2020 NR can achieve latencies as low as 10 ms or even less [10], depending on the hop count and specific use cases, making it suitable for real-time control and communication in applications, such as industrial automation and robotics. LoRa, on the other hand, has a typical latency ranging from 100 ms to several seconds. ZigBee latency is

Fig. 1. Illustrative example of an IoT mesh network with an indoor positioning system employing an onboard DOA estimation.

generally around 30–100 ms [11], while Bluetooth latency varies by version and application, with classic Bluetooth typically ranging from 30–100 ms. This higher latency is acceptable in many IoT applications where real-time data is not critical, such as environmental monitoring or smart metering.

While DECT-2020 NR can be power-efficient given the scale of operations it supports, it is optimized for devices that may have more power sources, such as industrial sensors or machinery. In contrast, ZigBee, Bluetooth, and LoRa are highly optimized for low power consumption, making them ideal for battery-powered devices in consumer and smart home applications. However, this optimization comes at the expense of lower range, data rate, and scalability.

A. Challenges

A key application of IoT technology is indoor localization [12]. By tracking the movement and location of inventory items or assets, IoT-based indoor localization improves inventory management, reduces loss, and enhances operational efficiency. In industrial settings, it monitors the movement of machinery and personnel, ensuring safety and optimizing workflows. For healthcare facilities or homes with elderly residents, it enables tracking patients or seniors, especially those with dementia.

Many radio-based solutions have been explored for localization. Some rely on received signal strength (RSS) [13] to locate devices. Others utilize time-of-arrival (TOA) [14] or low-cost carrier phase-based ranging [15]. Direction-of-arrival (DOA)-based systems, achieving submeter accuracy [16], [17], [18], [19], have gained traction. These systems leverage anchor nodes equipped with antenna arrays with known positions and mobile nodes emitting radio waves. Triangulating signals from a mobile node by at least three anchor nodes pinpoints its position.

DOA-based indoor localization must be low-cost and energy-efficient to operate in massive IoT mesh networks.

In such networks, a key feature is the integration of the cloud and local processing for data handling. While local processing at the node level allows for quick decision making and reduces the load on the network, the cloud processing offers advanced data analytics and storage capabilities [20].

Cloud-based processing for DOA-based indoor localization in massive IoT mesh networks, while appealing for its scalability, suffers from impracticalities as follows.

- 1) *High Data Transmission*: Mobile nodes would emit radio waves, and anchor nodes would capture these as in-phase and quadrature (IQ) samples. Subsequently, these anchor nodes would need to transmit the collected data to the cloud using a multihop path. Upon receiving the data, the cloud would process it to estimate the DOA and positions of the mobile nodes. However, each data payload could consist of hundreds of bytes. The size of these data payloads is calculated with the following equation:

$$\text{Data Payload Size} = M \times N \times N_b \quad (1)$$

where M is the number of antennas in the array, N is the number of samples per antenna, and N_b is the number of bytes per sample.

- 2) *Battery Drain*: The constant transmission of such large payloads across multihop paths would rapidly deplete the battery life of devices.
- 3) *Increased Network Traffic*: The consistent need to transmit large volumes of data would lead to network congestion, increased latency, and diminished overall network performance.

A more efficient and cost-effective solution is an onboard DOA estimation at anchor nodes as depicted in Fig. 1. This localized processing requires transmitting data payload comprised of estimated DOAs. This strategy significantly reduces data volume since the data requirement for the azimuth and elevation angles is merely 8 bytes, considering the common 32-bit computer architecture of IoT devices.

However, integrating DOA-based localization within massive IoT mesh networks presents a substantial challenge due to battery-powered nodes [21]. This necessitates energy-efficient DOA solutions, achieved by minimizing execution and transmission times. Execution time reduction requires DOA algorithm optimization. Reducing transmission time through shorter symbol duration compromises the number of samples, potentially impacting DOA accuracy.

Given the importance of cost-effectiveness, it is essential to minimize the number of antennas and electronic components used in antenna arrays. Therefore, DOA solutions for massive IoT mesh networks require a delicate balancing act. Optimizing energy consumption and accuracy while adhering to cost constraints demands innovative approaches that effectively manage these tradeoffs.

B. Motivations and Contributions

This research investigates the feasibility of an affordable and energy-efficient DOA-based localization system for the DECT 2020 NR standard, which lacks a native positioning feature.

The key contributions of our study include as follows.

- 1) An introduction of a potential cost-effective positioning feature for DECT 2020 NR, utilizing array sequential sampling. In this approach, each antenna takes turns sampling the OFDM signal in a time-division manner.
- 2) An innovative DOA method tailored for single Line-of-Sight (LOS) OFDM signals and compatible with array sequential sampling.
- 3) Our experiments move beyond the typical average-value accuracy assessment. Our approach examines execution time, energy consumption, and memory footprint using detailed angular and positional statistics. It provides a comprehensive evaluation in a simulated indoor environment with noise and a multipath channel featuring a dominant LOS component.
- 4) Software and hardware implementations of some digital baseband operations to refine the evaluation of the localization solution.

C. Organization

The manuscript is structured as follows. Section II reviews the related studies for OFDM DOA estimations, highlighting the key distinctions between our research and these prior studies. Section III presents a signal model for array sequential sampling, details the receiver's operational process, and describes the key system components. Section IV explicates the implemented DOA and positioning methods. Sections V and VI describe the simulation and embedded software experiments, respectively, and analyze their results. Section VII identifies our research limitations which open up new avenues for future endeavors. Section VIII concludes the manuscript.

II. RELATED WORK

Table I outlines the main mathematical notations present in this article, while Table II presents a comparative analysis of relevant studies.

TABLE I
MATHEMATICAL NOTATION

N -size identity matrix	\mathbf{I}_N
$N \times M$ -size zero matrix	$\mathbf{0}_{N \times M}$
M -size unitary column vector	$\mathbf{1}_M$
The estimation of x	\hat{x}
Inverse	$(\bullet)^{-1}$
Complex conjugate	$(\bullet)^*$
Transpose	$(\bullet)^T$
Conjugate transpose	$(\bullet)^H$
Real part	$\text{Re}\{\bullet\}$
Expectation	$\mathbb{E}\{\bullet\}$
Imaginary unit	$j = \sqrt{-1}$
Absolute value	$ \bullet $
Diag operator	$\text{diag}\{\bullet\}$
Floor function	$\lfloor \bullet \rfloor$
Euclidean norm	$\ \bullet\ $
Hadamard product	\odot
2-argument arctangent	$\arctan2(\bullet)$
Fourier transform	$\mathcal{F}\{\bullet\}$
Discrete Fourier transform	$\text{DFT}\{\bullet\}$
Inverse cosine	$\arccos(\bullet)$
Exponential function	$\exp\{\bullet\}$
Max function	$\max\{\bullet\}$
Arguments of the minima	$\arg \min\{\bullet\}$
Linear span	$\text{span}\{\bullet\}$
Convolution	\otimes

Xu et al. [22] tackled the complexity and limited scope of DOA estimation for coherent multipath channels. They constructed a virtual array, applied frequency-domain smoothing, and utilized the estimation of signal parameters via rotational invariance techniques (ESPRITs) for DOA estimation using a uniform circular antenna (UCA). Additionally, they employed 1-D multiple signal classification (MUSIC) for TOA estimation. In simulations, conducted under low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) conditions ($< 5\text{dB}$), the DOA method achieves root mean-squared errors (RMSEs) ranging from 1° to 0.1° .

However, the study is limited to three scenarios with preset the azimuth and elevation angles and up to three coherent multipath components. It lacks a comprehensive channel model, such as ray tracing or clustered delay line (CDL), and solely relies on RMSEs, offering partial statistical insights.

The study in [23] introduces two joint DOA and direction of departure (DOD) estimation methods for multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO)-OFDM systems, focusing on beamforming. These methods include the expectation-maximization (EM) algorithm and a two-stage Bayesian EM (BEM). They determine DOA and DOD by estimating channel impulse responses in a uniform linear array (ULA) under a millimeter waves (mmWave) channel model. However, their accuracy evaluation is limited to normalized mean-square error (NMSE) in simulations, and the study does not perform positioning estimation due to its beamforming-centric approach.

Wu et al. [24] proposed a 2-D discrete fourier transform (2-D DFT)-based DOA algorithm and a 3-D two-stage weighted least square (TSWLS)-based positioning method for mmWave systems, using a uniform planar array (UPA). They conduct their experiments in a time division duplex (TDD) mmWave multiple input single output (MISO) channel, incorporating angular estimation error variance into 3-D positioning for enhanced accuracy.

TABLE II
COMPARATIVE OVERVIEW OF RELATED PAPERS

Reference	DOA Method	Position Method	Array Type	Channel Model	Measurements
[22]	UCA-ESPRIT	None	UCA multiple RF chains	Scenario-based model	Angular accuracy TOA accuracy
[23]	BEM and EM	None	ULA multiple RF chains	mmWave	Angular accuracy
[24]	2D DFT	TSWLS	UPA multiple RF chains	TDD mmWave MISO	Angular accuracy Positional accuracy
[25]	MUSIC-type	Analytical Solution	ULA multiple RF chains	IEEE 802.11 Indoor	Angular accuracy TOA accuracy Position accuracy
[26]	MUSIC	None	ULA multiple RF chains	Scenario-based model	Angular accuracy TOA accuracy
[27]	EKF	EKF	ULA multiple RF chains	Real-world	Angular accuracy Position accuracy
This paper	ESPRIT-type	MinSE + BFGS	L-shape a single RF chain	Ray Tracing + AWGN	Angular metrics Position metrics Execution time Energy consumption Memory footprint

Similarly, Zhou et al. [25] employed MUSIC for DOA and channel coefficients for TOA estimation in ULAs with OFDM signals in an IEEE 802.11 indoor channel model. Both studies report mean-squared errors (MSEs) in simulations, but Wu et al. additionally provide data on positional and angular accuracy variance.

Yu et al. [26] developed DOA and TOA estimation methods for ULAs for OFDM signals. They apply MUSIC with an improved eigenvector method. However, this method relies on an inefficient 2-D search for the azimuth and elevation angles, forgoing a detailed channel model and instead defining a limited set of signal parameters.

The study in [27] investigates an advanced angular estimation and transmitter position tracking technique using software-defined radio devices equipped with ULAs and conceptualized for 5G ultradense networks. Utilizing a two-stage extended Kalman filter (EKF), the method initially estimates DOA and subsequently determines position, supported by an edge-cloud positioning engine that accounts for the location of each anchor node. However, this research is limited to 2-D localization using an ULA and offers only limited real-world trial insights.

Our research distinctively uses a uniform L-shaped array with a single radio-frequency (RF) chain, setting it apart from the referenced studies. We conduct our experiments in a virtual furnished room, mimicking real-world conditions with noise and a multipath channel, utilizing the ray tracing channel model. A notable innovation in our study is the development of a new DOA method, designed specifically for resource-constrained IoT devices. This method, optimized for efficient single DOA estimation, is well-suited for array sequential sampling.

In our analysis, we go beyond the typical average value metrics, which are susceptible to distortion by extreme outliers. We instead use boxplots in our analysis, offering a more thorough representation of data distribution and skewness.

TABLE III
DECT 2020 NR WAVEFORM

Parameter	Symbol	Values
Carrier frequency	f_c	1.9 GHz
Number of subcarriers	L	64
Active subcarriers	L_a	56
Subcarrier spacing	Δf	27 kHz
Cyclic prefix length	l_{cp}	8
Symbol duration	T_{sym}	41.667 μs
Sampling frequency	f_s	1.728 MHz
Sampling Time	T_s	0.5787 μs
Reference data	X_{ref}	$e^{j\pi/4}$

Additionally, we evaluate the execution time, energy consumption, and memory footprint of our novel DOA method. These performance metrics are crucial for battery-operated IoT devices, as any solution must adhere to their limited computational and power resources. Moreover, we apply a minimum square error (MinSE)-based model for position estimation and use the Broyden–Fletcher–Goldfarb–Shanno (BFGS) optimization algorithm to find the MinSE.

III. ARRAY SEQUENTIAL SAMPLING

In our study, we analyze a scenario where a stationary, far-field transmitter broadcasts an LOS OFDM signal to a receiver, adhering to DECT 2020 NR waveform parameters (see Table III) [28], the only waveform currently in use at the time of this writing. This signal traverses a time-invariant and frequency-selective channel, along with additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN). Given our focus on radio direction finding, we adopt the standard practice of assuming an ideal receiver to exclude hardware imperfections, such as time and frequency mismatches, thus simplifying our analysis.

Fig. 2. Depiction of an incoming signal impinging on a uniform L-shaped array, with identical antennas (black dots) at azimuth (θ) and elevation (ϕ) angles.

We utilize uniform L-shaped arrays as opting for this design allows for a simpler structure with fewer antennas compared to traditional rectangular antenna arrays. Thus, uniform L-shaped arrays offer a more economical and energy-efficient solution which is particularly beneficial in massive IoT applications, albeit at the expense of some angular resolution. The array lies in the xy -plane as shown in Fig. 2. It comprises two equal ULAs of \tilde{M} identical antennas, one on each axis, totalling $M = 2\tilde{M} - 1$ antennas. The distance between two adjacent antennas is half of the OFDM signal's carrier wavelength (λ).

Typically, each antenna in an array needs its own RF chain, which increases power consumption, size, and cost. To address these issues in massive IoT contexts, we consider a single RF chain shared across all antennas via an RF switch, allowing sequential signal sampling. This method, while not allowing simultaneous signal sampling, maintains the ability to aggregate signals from all antennas, potentially offering a more power-efficient and cost-effective solution.

The receiver time-divides the OFDM signal into an alternate series of sample and switch slots, as illustrated in Fig. 3. The antenna samples the signal in the sample slot and the switch occurs in the switch slot. The receiver employs a round-Robin switch pattern in which during each sequence, the first antenna samples first, followed by the second, and so on until the final antenna. The receiver then repeats the sequence until the OFDM symbol ends.

We define the slot duration as T_r . Therefore, when the RF switch selects an antenna, the sample slot duration is T_r , during which the receiver can sample the signal once. For simplicity, we assume that when the RF switch selects an antenna, the receiver immediately samples the received signal making the antenna selection time equal to the antenna sampling time.

Following the round-Robin switch pattern, the RF switch alternates between antennas at the interval of $2T_r$, as a result, the antenna sampling interval is $T_a = 2MT_r$, leading to an antenna sampling frequency of $f_a = f_r/(2M)$ where $f_r = 1/T_r$ is the slot rate. Fig. 4 illustrates the received signal of a given antenna. The intervals between yellow lines correspond to the duration of the sample slot, in which the antenna selection

times $t_0, t_0 + T_a, t_0 + 2T_a$ are equal to their instantaneous sampling times.

Our DOA technique utilizes the antennas' frequency response to estimate the DOA. Thus, per the Nyquist–Shannon theorem [29], to compute the antenna frequency response accurately, the antenna sampling frequency should be at least twice the signal bandwidth to prevent aliasing (see Fig. 5). However, for OFDM signals, only active subcarriers carry information. Therefore, the antenna sampling frequency should be at least twice the active subcarrier bandwidth

$$\begin{aligned} f_a &\geq 2\left(\frac{L_a\Delta f}{2}\right) \implies \frac{f_r}{2M} \geq L_a\Delta f \\ \implies f_r &\geq 2ML_a\Delta f. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Therefore, we need to increase the slot rate (f_r) by at least $2M$ times the bandwidth of active subcarriers. We set $f_r = 2Mf_s$, ensuring it exceeds the minimum requirement since

$$f_r = 2ML\Delta f = 2Mf_s > 2ML_a\Delta f. \quad (3)$$

However, increasing f_r raises both the energy requirements for powering electronic devices and costs due to the need for higher analog-to-digital converter (ADC) sampling rates. To mitigate these issues, we propose transmitting an OFDM signal with fewer active subcarriers, allowing a reduction in f_r without introducing aliasing. By halving or quartering the number of active subcarriers, we correspondingly reduce f_r , balancing energy consumption and cost-efficiency against the potential impact on DOA estimation accuracy due to fewer samples per OFDM symbol.

Furthermore, the slot duration must surpass the RF switch's settling time, which is the time needed for the signal to stabilize post-switching. We find that many single pole single throw (SPST) integrated circuits (ICs) achieve nanosecond-level settling times, well below the slot duration used in our study. For example, the ADRF5080 SP8T Switch [30], a compact millimeter-sized RF switch, boasts a settling time of merely 50 ns.

A. Signal Model

Fig. 6 illustrates the workflow of the signal model at the receiver. To enhance readability, each process is labeled with a corresponding section number, which offers a detailed textual description. Importantly, while the figure depicts an ULA for clearer visualization in a 2-D format, the receiver in this research employs an L-shaped antenna array as mentioned previously.

1) *Signal Reception*: As previously mentioned, this model involves a transmitter sending a random OFDM signal to an antenna array, characterizing the system as a single-input–multiple-output (SIMO) configuration. The channel impulse response at the m th antenna is based on a tapped-delay-line (TDL) filter given by

$$\begin{aligned} h_m(t) &= \sum_{i=1}^I \gamma_i \delta(t - \tau_i) \otimes \delta(t - \xi_{i,m}) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^I \gamma_i \delta(t - \tau_i - \xi_{i,m}) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 3. Illustrative example of the round-Robin switch pattern considering an array composed of seven antennas.

Fig. 4. Illustrative example of a signal received by an antenna, its sample slot duration (T_r) between yellow lines and antenna sampling times t_o , $t_o + T_a$, and $t_o + 2T_a$.

Fig. 5. To prevent aliasing, the antenna sampling frequency (f_a) should be at least twice the baseband signal bandwidth ($W/2$), creating a clear separation between spectral copies, as indicated in red.

Fig. 6. Theoretical workflow and delay times.

such that $\delta(t)$ is the Dirac delta function, and the other terms are defined as described.

- 1) I denotes the total number of signal components, including LOS and multipath components.
- 2) τ_i represents the propagation time for the i th signal component to reach the first antenna, with τ_1 indicating the arrival time of the LOS component.
- 3) γ_i is the random complex attenuation of the i th signal component, incorporating the antenna gain $g(\theta_i, \phi_i)$, where θ_i and ϕ_i indicate the azimuth and elevation angles, respectively, for the i th component at the receiver. The function $g(\theta, \phi)$ denotes the far-field antenna pattern, which is equal across identical antennas and hence lacks an antenna-specific index.
- 4) $\xi_{i,m}$ is the additional propagation time for the i th component to reach the m th antenna relative to the first antenna.

That delay depends on the DOA, more precisely

$$\xi_{i,m} = \frac{\Delta x_m \cos(\theta_i) \sin(\phi_i) + \Delta y_m \sin(\theta_i) \sin(\phi_i)}{v} \quad (5)$$

where v is the speed of the waveform, and Δx_m and Δy_m are the positional difference between the m th and first antennas in the xy plane.

From the channel impulse response in (4), we can derive the received passband random OFDM signal at the m th antenna as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} y_m(t) &= \Re\{x(t)e^{j2\pi f_c t} \otimes h_m(t) + n_m(t)\} \\ &= \Re\left\{\sum_{i=1}^I \gamma_i x(t - \tau_i - \xi_{i,m}) e^{j2\pi f_c (t - \tau_i - \xi_{i,m})} + n_m(t)\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

for $0 \leq t \leq T_{\text{sym}}$. We omit the cyclic prefix for convenience, and the details are as follows.

Fig. 7. Illustration of the SIMO system.

1) The complex envelope

$$x(t) = \sum_{l=-L/2}^{L/2-1} X_{\text{ref}} e^{j\pi l \Delta f t}. \quad (7)$$

2) X_{ref} is the reference data (see Table III).

3) $n_m(t)$ represents AWGN at the m th antenna.

To simplify (6), we can encapsulate the term τ_i by defining

$$z_i(t) = \gamma_i x(t - \tau_i) e^{-j2\pi f_c \tau_i}. \quad (8)$$

This leads to the following expression:

$$y_m(t) = \text{Re} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^I z_i(t - \xi_{i,m}) e^{j2\pi f_c (t - \xi_{i,m})} \right\} + n_m(t). \quad (9)$$

Fig. 7 illustrates the SIMO system with the channel impulse response defined in (4) and each antenna output given by (9). Fig. 8 visually represents multipath propagation in 2-D, highlighting the LOS signal in red alongside its multipath components. In this figure, each component is associated with its propagation time, complex attenuation, and DOA. Note that, additional propagation within the antenna array is not illustrated.

2) *RF Switch*: The RF switch employs a round-Robin switching pattern, alternating between antennas at intervals $2T_r$. It is important to reiterate that when the RF switch selects an antenna, the selection duration is T_r (see Fig. 4), during which the receiver can sample the signal once. For simplicity, we assume that when the RF switch selects an antenna m , the receiver immediately samples $y_m(t)$ in the baseband, making the antenna selection time equal to the sampling time.

Fig. 8. Illustrative example of the propagation scenario adopted in this research: LOS signal with its multipath components.

Fig. 9. Sampling times for the round-Robin switch pattern where each color represents a different antenna.

Due to the RF switch, the m th antenna starts sampling at $\zeta_m = 2(m-1)T_r$, after the first antenna. Fig. 9 illustrates the sampling times in the round-Robin switch pattern, where each color represents the sampling time of a different antenna.

Fig. 10 provides an illustrative example of the received signal and sampling times for each antenna in the case of a single-component signal. As depicted, the signal arrives at antenna m on $\tau_1 + \xi_{1,m}$. However, due to the RF switch, the m th antenna begins sampling only after ζ_m . Consequently, the samples experience a total time delay of $\tau_1 + \xi_{1,m} + \zeta_m$, which we use as the origin of the coordinate system for clarity in visualization.

3) *Complex Down-Conversion*: Subsequently, the signal of the m th antenna defined in (9) undergoes a complex downconversion to the baseband and is sampled at intervals T_a . Furthermore, we adopt an ideal sampling model [31] characterized by an infinite series of instantaneous impulses. Accordingly, we need to assume further the OFDM signal is periodic, with the transmitter continuously sending the OFDM symbol ad infinitum. The baseband signal of antenna m , therefore, is

$$s_m(t) = \sum_{i=1}^I \left(z_i(t - \zeta_m - \xi_{i,m}) e^{-j2\pi f_c \xi_{i,m}} + n_m(t) \right) s_\delta(t) \quad (10)$$

such that $s_\delta(t)$ is the ideal sampling function

$$s_\delta(t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \delta(t - nT_a). \quad (11)$$

More precisely, $s_m(t)$ is a discrete-time signal consisting of an infinite series of samples. Each sample is a random variable indexed by time, meaning $s_m(t)$ is a discrete-time random process.

Fig. 10. Illustrative example of the received signal and sampling times for each antenna of a single-component signal.

Fig. 11. Illustrative representation of (10).

Fig. 11 visually represents (10), illustrating the input pass-band signal $y_m(t)$ which is delayed by ζ_m , sampled at intervals of T_a , and then subjected to complex downconversion, resulting in the output signal $s_m(t)$.

4) *Fourier Transform*: Hence, the frequency response of the m th antenna is

$$\begin{aligned} \check{S}_m(f) &= \mathcal{F}\{s_m(t)\} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^I \mathcal{F}\left\{ \left(z_i(t - \zeta_m - \xi_{i,m}) e^{-j2\pi f_c \xi_{i,m}} + n_m(t) \right) s_\delta(t) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 12. Spectral replicas of the sampled signal and the LPF.

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{i=1}^I \mathcal{F}\left\{ z_i(t - \zeta_m - \xi_{i,m}) e^{-j2\pi f_c \xi_{i,m}} + n_m(t) \right\} \\ &\quad \otimes \mathcal{F}\{s_\delta(t)\} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^I \left(Z_i(f) e^{-j2\pi f_c \xi_{i,m}} e^{-j2\pi f (\zeta_m + \xi_{i,m})} + N_m(f) \right) \\ &\quad \otimes \left(f_a \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \delta(f - n f_a) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

5) *Low-Pass Filter*: The sampled signal generates spectral replicas in the frequency domain. We use an ideal low-pass filter (LPF) to obtain the antenna frequency response centered on DC (see Fig. 12)

$$\begin{aligned} S_m(f) &= \text{LPF}\{\check{S}_m(f)\} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^I Z_i(f) e^{-j2\pi f_c \xi_{i,m}} e^{-j2\pi f (\zeta_m + \xi_{i,m})} + N_m(f) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

such that the frequency response of that LPF is

$$G(f) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{f_a}, & -\left(\frac{L}{2}\right)\Delta f \leq f \leq \left(\frac{L}{2} - 1\right)\Delta f \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

a) *Narrowband condition*: In wireless communication, the narrowband condition refers to a scenario where the signal bandwidth (B) is much smaller than the inverse of the delay spread (τ_{\max}) [32]. Mathematically, the narrowband condition can be expressed as

$$B \ll \frac{1}{\tau_{\max}}. \quad (15)$$

This condition pertains to signal propagation between receivers and transmitters. In array signal processing, the narrowband condition is defined similarly, however, τ_{\max} represents the maximum propagation delay within the antenna array [33]. This delay corresponds to the longest path that a signal travels across the array, which is the distance between the first and the m th antenna, in our particular case.

As such, we define τ_{\max} for uniform L-shaped arrays as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{\max} &= \max_{\theta, \phi} \frac{\Delta x_M \cos(\theta) \sin(\phi) + \Delta y_M \sin(\theta) \sin(\phi)}{v} \\ &\implies \tau_{\max} \geq \xi_{i,m} \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, I, m = 1, \dots, M \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

in which $\theta \in [-\pi, \pi)$ and $\phi \in [0, \pi/2]$. The inequality of (16), comes from the definition of τ_{\max} . Specifically, the

maximum propagation delay (t_{\max}) is equal or greater than the propagation delay of individual signal components ($\xi_{i,m}$). As a consequence

$$|2\pi f \tau_{\max}| \ll 1, \quad \text{for all } |f| \leq \frac{L}{2} \Delta f \quad (17)$$

which implies

$$e^{-j2\pi f \xi_{i,m}} \approx 1, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, I, m = 1, \dots, M. \quad (18)$$

In other words, the phase shifts caused by the signal's bandwidth are minimal when the signal propagates within the antenna arrays. Based on (18), we can simplify (13) to

$$\begin{aligned} S_m(f) &\approx \sum_{i=1}^I Z_i(f) \underbrace{e^{-j2\pi f \xi_{i,m}}}_{a_m(\theta_i, \phi_i)} \underbrace{e^{-2\pi f \zeta_m}}_{\kappa_{m,f}} + N_m(f) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^I Z_i(f) a_m(\theta_i, \phi_i) \kappa_{m,f} + N_m(f). \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Here, $a_m(\theta_i, \phi_i)$ represents the phase shift attributable to the relative position of the m th antenna compared to the first antenna, and $\kappa_{m,f}$ signifies the phase shift resulting from sequential sampling.

Consequently, the narrowband approximation implies that phase shifts in the signal bandwidth become negligible during the propagation of the signal within an antenna array and the phase shift at the carrier frequency (the DOA), $a_m(\theta_i, \phi_i)$, predominates.

This assumption is particularly relevant in IoT contexts, where antenna arrays often consist of a limited number of elements, resulting in a small τ_{\max} . For example, we found that uniform L-shaped arrays typically incorporate three to four elements per ULA.

b) *Array responses*: We arrange the antenna frequency responses as follows:

$$\mathbf{S}(f)^T \triangleq [S_1(f) \quad S_2(f) \quad \dots \quad S_M(f)]. \quad (20)$$

Namely, $\mathbf{S}(f)$ is the array frequency response which is a random vector of M frequency domain random processes indexed by antennas. Fig. 13 illustrates a single realization of $\mathbf{S}(f)$. That arrangement enables the derivation of the array responses of the sequentially sampled OFDM signal

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{S}(f) &= \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{i=1}^I Z_i(f) a_1(\theta_i, \phi_i) \kappa_{1,f} + N_1(f) \\ \sum_{i=1}^I Z_i(f) a_2(\theta_i, \phi_i) \kappa_{2,f} + N_2(f) \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{i=1}^I Z_i(f) a_M(\theta_i, \phi_i) \kappa_{M,f} + N_M(f) \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} a_1(\theta_1, \phi_1) \kappa_{1,f} & \dots & a_1(\theta_I, \phi_I) \kappa_{1,f} \\ a_2(\theta_1, \phi_1) \kappa_{2,f} & \dots & a_2(\theta_I, \phi_I) \kappa_{2,f} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ a_M(\theta_1, \phi_1) \kappa_{M,f} & \dots & a_M(\theta_I, \phi_I) \kappa_{M,f} \end{bmatrix} \\ &\quad \begin{bmatrix} Z_1(f) \\ Z_2(f) \\ \vdots \\ Z_I(f) \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{N}(f) \\ &= \mathbf{K} \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\phi}) \mathbf{Z}(f) + \mathbf{N}(f) \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Fig. 13. Visual representation of $\mathbf{S}(f)$ as defined in (20).

such that

$$\mathbf{K} \triangleq \text{diag}[\kappa_{1,f} \quad \kappa_{2,f} \quad \dots \quad \kappa_{M,f}] \quad (22)$$

$$\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\phi}) \triangleq [\mathbf{a}(\theta_1, \phi_1) \quad \mathbf{a}(\theta_2, \phi_2) \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{a}(\theta_I, \phi_I)] \quad (23)$$

$$\mathbf{a}(\theta_i, \phi_i)^T \triangleq [a_1(\theta_i, \phi_i) \quad \dots \quad a_M(\theta_i, \phi_i)] \quad (24)$$

$$\mathbf{Z}(f) \triangleq [Z_1(f) \quad Z_2(f) \quad \dots \quad Z_I(f)] \quad (25)$$

$$\mathbf{N}(f) \triangleq \text{diag}[N_1(f) \quad N_2(f) \quad \dots \quad N_M(f)]. \quad (26)$$

Here, $\mathbf{a}(\theta_i, \phi_i)$ denotes the array response for the i th signal component. In our case, in which antennas have an identical radiation pattern, the array response essentially represents the signal's phase shift caused by the displacement between antennas, which is influenced by the signal's DOA.

Equation (21) demonstrates that the array responses incorporate phase shifts from sequential sampling, affecting DOA estimation accuracy. Therefore, to accurately estimate the DOA, it is essential to remove these phase shifts as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathbf{S}}(f) &\triangleq \mathbf{K}^H \mathbf{K} \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\phi}) \mathbf{Z}(f) + \mathbf{K}^H \mathbf{N}(f) \\ &= \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\phi}) \mathbf{Z}(f) + \mathbf{K}^H \mathbf{N}(f). \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

For indoor positioning, the receiver must accurately estimate the DOA of the direct signal path to perform triangulation. In our scenario, this direct signal path corresponds to the LOS component. However, the LOS component is often compromised by interference from multipath signals. Multipath interference degrades the accuracy of DOA estimation [34], [35]. To address this challenge, the following steps explain a technique for separating the array response of the LOS component from its multipath counterparts.

c) *LOS array response separation*: Assuming the signal components to be uncorrelated with the noise and wide-sense stationary (WSS) with zero mean. In practical terms, the array sampling time can be short enough for the signal to be approximated WSS [36]. The frequency domain correlation

matrix, commonly known as the cross-spectral density (CSD) matrix [37], of the received signal between antennas is

$$\mathbf{C}_{\tilde{\mathbf{S}}\tilde{\mathbf{S}}}(f) \triangleq \mathbb{E}\left\{\tilde{\mathbf{S}}(f)\tilde{\mathbf{S}}(f)^H\right\} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} r_{11}(f) & r_{12}(f) & \dots & r_{1M}(f) \\ r_{21}(f) & r_{22}(f) & \dots & r_{2M}(f) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ r_{M1}(f) & r_{M2}(f) & \dots & r_{MM}(f) \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

in which $r_{ij}(f) \triangleq \mathbb{E}\{S_i(f)S_j(f)^H\}$ is the CSD between received signals of antennas i and j . The CSD quantifies how the power of two signals is distributed across different frequencies. In particular, $r_{ii}(f)$ is the power spectral density (PSD) of the received signal in the antenna i . From (28), we derive

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{C}_{\tilde{\mathbf{S}}\tilde{\mathbf{S}}}(f) &= \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\phi}) \underbrace{\mathbb{E}\left\{\mathbf{Z}(f)\mathbf{Z}(f)^H\right\}}_{\mathbf{C}_{\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}}(f)} \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\phi})^H + n_0 \mathbf{I}_M(f) \\ &= \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\phi}) \mathbf{C}_{\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}}(f) \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\phi})^H + n_0 \mathbf{I}_M(f), \nu \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

in which

$$\mathbf{C}_{\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}}(f) \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} q_{11}(f) & q_{12}(f) & \dots & q_{1I}(f) \\ q_{21}(f) & q_{22}(f) & \dots & q_{2I}(f) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ q_{I1}(f) & q_{I2}(f) & \dots & q_{II}(f) \end{bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

is the CSD matrix of signal components and $q_{ij}(f) \triangleq \mathbb{E}\{S_i(f)S_j(f)^H\}$ is the CSD between signal components i and j .

Since the signal components have zero means, the covariance between them equals its correlation

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathbb{E}\left\{(S_i(f) - \mathbb{E}\{S_i(f)\})(S_j(f) - \mathbb{E}\{S_j(f)\})^H\right\} \\ &= \mathbb{E}\left\{S_i(f)S_j(f)^H\right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

Notably, zero-mean in the time domain implies zero-mean in the frequency domain for an arbitrary WSS random signal $x(t)$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}\{X(f)\} &= \mathbb{E}\left\{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x(t)e^{-j2\pi ft} dt\right\} \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \mathbb{E}\{x(t)\}e^{-j2\pi ft} dt = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

Additionally, the signal components are typically assumed to be approximately uncorrelated [34], thus covariance between signal components is near zero. From (31), it also means that their correlations are near zero, $q_{ij} \approx 0$ for $i \neq j$. Therefore, $\mathbf{C}_{\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}}$ is approximately a diagonal matrix whose diagonal elements (q_{ii}) represent the PSD of the signal components as follows:

$$\mathbf{C}_{\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}}(f) \approx \begin{bmatrix} q_{11}(f) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & q_{22}(f) & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & q_{II}(f). \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

Fig. 14. Illustrative heatmap of the eigenvalue decomposition of $\mathbf{C}_{\tilde{\mathbf{S}}\tilde{\mathbf{S}}}(f_o)$ highlighting the dominant eigenvector and eigenvalue for a given frequency f_o .

Moreover, a reasonable assumption in the literature regards signal components to arrive at distinct directions, and components with close or equal directions can be lumped together [38].

Let's consider the LOS component to have the highest PSD. To identify the array response of this component, we compute the dominant eigenvector of $\mathbf{C}_{\tilde{\mathbf{S}}\tilde{\mathbf{S}}}(f)$. This approach is effective because the dominant eigenvector corresponds to the signal direction with maximum variance [39], which in this context is equivalent to the maximum PSD. This relationship is well-known in multivariate statistics, particularly in principal component analysis (PCA), where the large datasets are reduced by focusing on their principal components (dominant eigenvectors) [40].

However, it is important to note that the dominant eigenvector is not necessarily equal to the LOS array response. But it closely aligns with that array response and can be considered approximately a scaled version, making it a reliable representation of the LOS component's direction in practical scenarios.

In summary, the eigenvalue decomposition of the CSD matrix, $\mathbf{C}_{\tilde{\mathbf{S}}\tilde{\mathbf{S}}}(f)$, enables the separation of the LOS signal's spatial characteristics (direction and PSD) from its multipath counterparts, improving the accuracy of DOA estimation. This is achieved by isolating the eigenvector associated with the highest eigenvalue. Fig. 14 illustrates this process using heatmap representations of the matrices for a given frequency f_o . That figure shows that the LOS PSD is the largest eigenvalue, enabling the retrieval of the corresponding eigenvector, which closely aligns with the LOS array response.

d) *Power average approach*: However, the LOS array response separation is based on a single CSD matrix. From the

Rayleigh's energy theorem [41], we can expand our technique by integrating the CSD matrix over the entire signal bandwidth (B). This theorem indicates that the total average power of the signal (in the time domain) is equal to the total area under the PSD curve. This allows us to determine the average power of the received signal components as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}_{\tilde{\mathbf{S}}} &\triangleq \frac{1}{T_{\text{sym}}} \int_B \mathbf{C}_{\tilde{\mathbf{S}}\tilde{\mathbf{S}}}(f) df \\ &= \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\phi}) \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{sym}}} \int_B (\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}}(f) + n_0 \mathbf{I}_I(f)) df \right) \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\phi})^H \\ &= \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\phi}) (\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{Z}} + \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{I}}) \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\phi})^H \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

in which

$$\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{Z}} \triangleq \frac{1}{T_{\text{sym}}} \int_B \mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}}(f) df \quad (35)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{I}} \triangleq \frac{n_0}{T_{\text{sym}}} \int_B \mathbf{I}_I(f) df. \quad (36)$$

In particular

$$\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{Z}} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} p_{11} & p_{12} & \cdots & p_{1I} \\ p_{21} & p_{22} & \cdots & p_{2I} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ p_{I1} & p_{I2} & \cdots & p_{II} \end{bmatrix} \quad (37)$$

where

$$p_{ij} \triangleq \frac{1}{T_{\text{sym}}} \int_B q_{ij}(f) df \quad (38)$$

is the average power over the entire bandwidth B of the CSD between the received signal components i and j . In particular, p_{ii} is the average power of the received signal component i .

The approach for the LOS array response separation based on $\mathbf{P}_{\tilde{\mathbf{S}}}$ follows the same procedure as the CSD matrix, with no distinct theoretical advantage over it. However, utilizing the average power presents a significant practical benefit. Since DOA algorithms can perform the DFT across multiple frequencies, averaging the CSD matrix over this range—rather than relying on a single CSD matrix estimation—can potentially improve the accuracy of the LOS array response estimation.

e) Final remarks: The model adheres to the standard practice of assuming uncorrelated signal components, AWGN, and zero-mean signals to simplify the analysis. These assumptions are widely accepted and can be found in numerous references within the literature [34], [35], [42], [43], [44], [45]. However, if the signals do not exhibit these characteristics, several existing techniques can be employed to address the challenges as follows.

- 1) *Colored Additive Noise:* In this scenario, a prewhitening technique can be applied before DOA estimation [43].
- 2) *Highly Correlated Signal Components:* When the signal components are highly correlated, the matrix $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}}$ deviates significantly from a diagonal form. To mitigate this issue, well-known decorrelation preprocessing techniques, such as forward-backward averaging and spatial smoothing can be used [34].

- 3) *Nonzero Mean Signals:* In cases where the signals are not zero-mean, it may be possible to estimate the covariance matrix instead of the correlation matrix by first calculating the mean of the received signal for each antenna.

B. Practical Operational Process

The signal model described in Section III-A presents a theoretical foundation for array sequential sampling. However, Fig. 15 depicts a more practical operational process of the ideal receiver using discrete signals, which is implemented in the proposed DOA algorithm.

Each antenna in the ideal receiver receives the passband OFDM signal $y_m(t)$ as defined in (9). The digital baseband Processing controls the RF Switch that alternates antennas at intervals of $2T_r$ following the round-Robin switching pattern. The RF chain then downconverts this signal, after which the ADC digitizes it into discrete format, represented by the series

$$s_m[n] = s_m(nT_a), \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, N-1 \quad (39)$$

where $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$ identifies each antenna. Notably, the ADC operates at the same frequency as the RF switch, thereby ensuring it captures one sample per sample slot.

Next, the receiver removes the guard interval and forwards the signal to the serial-to-parallel converter (SPC). The SPC acts as a buffer, storing mixed samples from each antenna following the order of the round-Robin switch pattern. It then segments these samples by their respective antennas, forming M vectors. Each vector, containing samples from a specific antenna, is then directed to its corresponding DFT. The DFT block calculates the DFT of the antenna response according to the series

$$S_m[k] = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} s_m[n] e^{-j\frac{2\pi kn}{N}}, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1 \quad (40)$$

where $S_m[k]$ is the discrete frequency representation of $S_m(f)$ as illustrated in Fig. 16. The frequency for the k th component, after shifting the zero-frequency component to the center of the spectrum, is defined by

$$f_k = \begin{cases} \frac{kf_a}{N}, & \text{for } k = 0, 1, \dots, \frac{N}{2} - 1 \\ -\frac{(N-k)f_a}{N}, & \text{for } k = \frac{N}{2}, \dots, N-1. \end{cases} \quad (41)$$

Finally, the DFT block transmits these frequency responses to the DOA method, which calculates the azimuth and elevation angles of the LOS component.

IV. IMPLEMENTED SOLUTIONS

A. DOA Method

ESPRIT [46], a subspace-based method, efficiently estimates the DOA by utilizing the dual shift-invariant property of specific planar arrays. Contrasting with methods like MUSIC, which require a laborious peak searching, ESPRIT streamlines this process, eliminating such steps. This method also compensates for modeling errors to a degree, reducing the need for comprehensive array calibration. Particularly, uniform L-shaped arrays facilitate ESPRIT's estimation of both the

Fig. 15. Illustrative overview of the ideal receiver's operational process.

Fig. 16. Illustrative representation, in blue, of the DFT of the m th antenna response ($S_m[k]$).

azimuth and elevation angles by separately using the x - and y -axis arrays. The array signal processing literature defines two subspaces as follows.

- 1) *Signal Subspace* (\mathcal{H}_s): Represents the set of the array response of the LOS component, in our specific case, and is expressed as

$$\mathcal{H}_s = \text{span}\{\mathbf{a}(\theta_1, \phi_1)\}. \quad (42)$$

- 2) *Noise Subspace* (\mathcal{H}_n): Represents the set of array responses where noise and interference (including multipath components) dominate, that is

$$\text{span}\{\mathbf{a}(\theta_2, \phi_2), \mathbf{a}(\theta_3, \phi_3), \dots, \mathbf{a}(\theta_I, \phi_I)\} \subset \mathcal{H}_n. \quad (43)$$

ESPRIT employs only the signal subspace for its operations. For an in-depth analysis of ESPRIT, refer to [35] or [43].

We have adapted the ESPRIT algorithm for sequential sampling using an L-shaped array, optimizing it specifically for single DOA estimation. To achieve this, we implemented three major modifications to the original ESPRIT algorithm, which we detail in the following paragraphs.

1) *Sequential Sampling Correction*: Algorithm 1 outlines our implemented DOA method, starting with antenna frequency responses $\{S_m[k]\}_{m=1}^M$. The method organizes these responses into a matrix \mathcal{S} and corrects for phase shifts from sequential sampling

$$\tilde{\mathcal{S}} = \mathcal{S} \odot \mathcal{K} \quad (44)$$

such that

$$\mathcal{S} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{S}[0] & \mathcal{S}[1] & \dots & \mathcal{S}[N-1] \end{bmatrix} \quad (45)$$

Fig. 17. Illustration of (45) which is the discrete version of $\mathbf{S}(f)$ as defined in (20).

$$\mathbf{S}[k]^T \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} S_1[k] & S_2[k] & \dots & S_M[k] \end{bmatrix} \quad (46)$$

$$\mathcal{K} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\kappa}_{1,f_0} & \bar{\kappa}_{1,f_1} & \dots & \bar{\kappa}_{1,f_{N-1}} \\ \bar{\kappa}_{2,f_0} & \bar{\kappa}_{2,f_1} & \dots & \bar{\kappa}_{2,f_{N-1}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \bar{\kappa}_{M,f_0} & \bar{\kappa}_{M,f_1} & \dots & \bar{\kappa}_{M,f_{N-1}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (47)$$

with $\bar{\kappa}_{m,f_k}$ being the inverse of κ_{m,f_k} . To be more clear, \mathcal{S} is the discrete version of $\mathbf{S}(f)$ as illustrated in Fig. 17.

2) *Fast Array Response Estimation*: Assuming the received signal to be second-moment ergodic, the method computes the sample correlation matrix of $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}$ as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}}_{\tilde{\mathcal{S}}} \triangleq \left(\frac{1}{N}\right) \tilde{\mathcal{S}} \tilde{\mathcal{S}}^H \quad (48)$$

which is the same operation as averaging the estimated CSD matrices over the whole bandwidth

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}}_{\tilde{\mathcal{S}}} = \left(\frac{1}{N}\right) \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \mathbf{S}[i] \mathbf{S}[i]^H \quad (49)$$

where $\mathbf{S}[i] \mathbf{S}[i]^H$ is the estimate of $\mathbf{C}_{\tilde{\mathcal{S}}}(f_i)$ making (49) the discrete version of (34).

The array response for the uniform L-shaped array is a combination of responses from its two orthogonal linear arrays

$$\mathbf{a}(\theta_i, \phi_i) \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ e^{-jv_i} \\ e^{-j2v_i} \\ \vdots \\ e^{-j(\mu_i + (\tilde{M}-1)v_i)} \\ e^{-j(2\mu_i + (\tilde{M}-1)v_i)} \\ \vdots \\ e^{-j((\tilde{M}-1)\mu_i + (\tilde{M}-1)v_i)} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1} \quad (50)$$

in which

$$\begin{aligned} v_i &\triangleq \frac{2\pi d}{\lambda} \sin(\theta_i) \sin(\phi_i) \\ \mu_i &\triangleq \frac{2\pi d}{\lambda} \cos(\theta_i) \sin(\phi_i) \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

where d is the distance between two consecutive antennas. For L-shaped arrays, ESPRIT segments the x - and y -axis arrays into four subarrays, as shown in Fig. 18. These subarrays enable the formulation of the dual shift-invariant equation to determine the azimuth and elevation angles

$$\begin{aligned} \underbrace{\mathbf{J}_1 \mathbf{a}(\theta_1, \phi_1)}_{\text{Subarray 1}} e^{-jv_1} &= \underbrace{\mathbf{J}_2 \mathbf{a}(\theta_1, \phi_1)}_{\text{Subarray 2}} \\ \underbrace{\mathbf{J}_3 \mathbf{a}(\theta_1, \phi_1)}_{\text{Subarray 3}} e^{-j\mu_1} &= \underbrace{\mathbf{J}_4 \mathbf{a}(\theta_1, \phi_1)}_{\text{Subarray 4}} \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

in which

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{J}_1 &\triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{\tilde{M}-1 \times \tilde{M}-1} & \mathbf{I}_{\tilde{M}-1} & \mathbf{0}_{\tilde{M}-1 \times 1} \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{J}_2 &\triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{\tilde{M}-1 \times \tilde{M}} & \mathbf{I}_{\tilde{M}-1} \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{J}_3 &\triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{\tilde{M}-1 \times 1} & \mathbf{I}_{\tilde{M}-1} & \mathbf{0}_{\tilde{M}-1 \times \tilde{M}-1} \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{J}_4 &\triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{\tilde{M}-1} & \mathbf{0}_{\tilde{M}-1 \times \tilde{M}} \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

However, given the unknown a priori array responses, ESPRIT estimates an element of the signal subspace from $\widehat{\mathbf{P}}_{\mathcal{S}}$.

The sample correlation matrix ($\widehat{\mathbf{P}}_{\mathcal{S}}$) is a Hermitian and positive semi-definite matrix. Therefore, Algorithm 1 can apply the power method [47] on $\widehat{\mathbf{P}}_{\mathcal{S}}$ to estimate the dominant eigenvector. The dominant eigenvector is the signal subspace as explained in Section III-A5b. This approach significantly reduces execution time and memory usage by circumventing the costly computations required for full eigenvalue decomposition. Notably, traditional EVD algorithms compute all eigenvalues and eigenvectors, leading to unnecessary memory consumption and increased computational overhead, making them one of the most complex numerical methods in linear algebra [47], [48], [49].

In our case, the power method iteratively computes the recurrence relation

$$\mathbf{v}_{k+1} = \frac{\widehat{\mathbf{P}}_{\mathcal{S}} \mathbf{v}_k}{\|\widehat{\mathbf{P}}_{\mathcal{S}} \mathbf{v}_k\|}, \quad k \geq 1 \quad (54)$$

in which $\mathbf{v}_1 = \mathbf{1}_M$. The iteration concludes when $\|\mathbf{v}_{k+1} - \mathbf{v}_k\|^2 < 10^{-6}$, indicating

$$\mathbf{v}_{k+1} \approx \underbrace{\rho_1 \mathbf{a}(\theta_1, \phi_1)}_{\mathbf{u}_s} \in \mathcal{H}_s \quad (55)$$

where ρ_1 is the linear coefficient or amplitude. Failure to meet this stopping criterion within 30 iterations indicates that Algorithm 1 has not succeeded in estimating the DOA.

3) *Simple Analytical Solver*: After computing \mathbf{u}_s , Algorithm 1 solves the estimated dual shift-invariant equation

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{J}_1 \mathbf{u}_s e^{-jv_1} &\approx \mathbf{J}_2 \mathbf{u}_s \\ \mathbf{J}_3 \mathbf{u}_s e^{-j\mu_1} &\approx \mathbf{J}_4 \mathbf{u}_s. \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

The system (56) is overdetermined, which is vulnerable to inaccuracies from signal subspace estimation, numerical errors, and imperfections in the array response. To mitigate these, Algorithm 1 applies the total least squares (TLSs), detailed in [50], to estimate $\exp -jv_1$ and $\exp -j\mu_1$.

However, instead of relying on numerical methods, Algorithm 1 analytically solves the estimated dual shift-invariant (56) via TLS, an improvement made possible by estimating only one DOA. For this purpose, Algorithm 1 calculates

$$\mathbf{E} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} (\mathbf{J}_1 \mathbf{u}_s)^H \\ (\mathbf{J}_2 \mathbf{u}_s)^H \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{J}_1 \mathbf{u}_s & \mathbf{J}_2 \mathbf{u}_s \end{bmatrix} + \epsilon \mathbf{I}_2 \quad (57)$$

with $\epsilon \mathbf{I}_2$ ($0 < \epsilon \ll 1$) to guarantee the positive-definiteness of \mathbf{E} .

Given that $\mathbf{E} \in \mathbb{C}^{2 \times 2}$ is Hermitian, it is diagonalizable and its eigenvalues are real according to the finite-dimensional spectral theorem [51]. Therefore, it is possible to apply TLS on \mathbf{E} . Let's denote Σ_1 and Σ_2 as the eigenvalues of \mathbf{E} , with $\Sigma_1 \geq \Sigma_2$. Algorithm 1 computes the smallest eigenvalue and its corresponding eigenvector analytically as follows:

$$\exp -j\widehat{v}_1 = -\frac{v_1}{v_2} \quad (58)$$

such that

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} e_{11} & e_{12} \\ e_{21} & e_{22} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{E}} \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \end{bmatrix} = \widehat{\Sigma}_2 \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (59)$$

$$\widehat{\Sigma}_2 = \min \left\{ \frac{b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2} \right\} \quad (60)$$

in which $a \triangleq 1$, $b \triangleq -(e_{11} - e_{22})$, and $c \triangleq e_{11}e_{22} - e_{12}e_{21}$. However, since \mathbf{E} is a positive-definite matrix, then its determinant is positive ($c > 0$), therefore

$$\widehat{\Sigma}_2 = \frac{-b - \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2}. \quad (61)$$

For details, refer to [52] or another introductory linear algebra book.

To estimate $\exp -j\mu_1$, Algorithm 1 replaces \mathbf{J}_1 and \mathbf{J}_2 with \mathbf{J}_3 and \mathbf{J}_4 in (57), and computes (58)–(60). Upon calculating $\exp -j\widehat{v}_1$ and $\exp -j\widehat{\mu}_1$, Algorithm 1 estimates the azimuth and elevation angles as per (65) and (66).

Fig. 18. Illustrative example of a seven-element uniform L-shaped array and its subarrays employed by ESPRIT.

Algorithm 1: DECT 2020 L-Shaped ESPRIT

Input: Frequency responses of antennas, $\{\{S_m[k]\}_{k=0}^{N-1}\}_{m=1}^M$.

Output: Azimuth and elevation angles of the LOS component, $(\hat{\theta}_1, \hat{\phi}_1)$.

- 1) Organize the inputs into a matrix \mathcal{S} and apply a phase compensation due to sequential sampling

$$\tilde{\mathcal{S}} = \mathcal{S} \odot \mathcal{K}. \quad (62)$$

- 2) Compute an element (\mathbf{u}_s) of the signal subspace as the dominant eigenvector of

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}}_{\tilde{\mathcal{S}}} = \left(\frac{1}{N} \right) \tilde{\mathcal{S}} \tilde{\mathcal{S}}^H \quad (63)$$

by applying the Power Method.

- 3) Estimate ν_1 and μ_1 by solving analytically the dual shift-invariant equation

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{J}_1 \mathbf{u}_s e^{-j\nu_1} &\approx \mathbf{J}_2 \mathbf{u}_s \\ \mathbf{J}_3 \mathbf{u}_s e^{-j\mu_1} &\approx \mathbf{J}_4 \mathbf{u}_s \end{aligned} \quad (64)$$

utilizing TLS.

- 4) Estimate the azimuth and elevation angles, that is

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\theta}_1 &= \arctan 2(\psi_1) \\ \hat{\phi}_1 &= \arccos(\|\psi_1\|) \end{aligned} \quad (65)$$

such that

$$\psi_1 = - \frac{\arctan 2(e^{-j\nu_1}) + j \arctan 2(e^{-j\mu_1})}{\left(\frac{2\pi d}{\lambda} \right)}. \quad (66)$$

B. Positioning Method

After estimating the DOA between a transmitter and each receiver, it is possible to apply triangulation to evaluate the position of the former as long as the latter's locations are known. Let $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the unknown position of the transmitter, and $\mathbf{r}_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the known position of the receiver k , for $k = 1, 2, \dots, R$, where $R \geq 3$. The estimated DOA between the transmitter and a receiver k is given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{d}}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\hat{\theta}_k) \cos(\hat{\phi}_k) \\ \sin(\hat{\theta}_k) \cos(\hat{\phi}_k) \\ \sin(\hat{\phi}_k) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (67)$$

Fig. 19. Illustration of the positioning method in 2-D.

With a direction and a point, we can form a parametric equation of a line for each receiver, that is

$$\hat{\mathbf{l}}_k(t) = \mathbf{r}_k + t\hat{\mathbf{d}}_k. \quad (68)$$

The transmitter's position is a point that minimizes the sum of distances to each line. From the Euclidean geometry, the shortest distance between a point, say $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, and a line can be expressed as

$$\text{dist}(\hat{\mathbf{l}}_k, \mathbf{x}) = \frac{\|(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{r}_k) \times \hat{\mathbf{d}}_k\|}{\|\hat{\mathbf{d}}_k\|}. \quad (69)$$

From (69), we can set up an optimization problem to estimate \mathbf{p} as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{x}} \sum_{k=1}^R \text{dist}(\hat{\mathbf{l}}_k, \mathbf{x})^2. \quad (70)$$

Equation (70) refers to the MinSE problem. Fig. 19 illustrates the positioning method in 2-D for clarity in visualization, though the technique is designed for 3-D positioning.

To solve (70), we turn to quasi-Newton methods, a suite of algorithms specifically tailored for unconstrained optimization. Among them, we employ the BFGS algorithm [53] which could be fairly time consuming for constrained IoT devices. However, the positioning method is executed in the cloud composed of high-performance servers.

While the problem's convexity cannot be guaranteed, the situation can significantly improve when considering an indoor environment with known dimensions. In these cases, we can expedite the minimization process by constraining the multivariable \mathbf{x} to conform with the specific size of the indoor setting, effectively transforming the problem into a constrained optimization task.

V. SIMULATION EXPERIMENTS

The experiment aims to assess the angular and position accuracy of our novel localization system. We also examine the feasibility of lowering the slot rate to below $f_r = 2Mf_s$.

TABLE IV
SIMULATION PARAMETERS IN MATLAB

Parameter	Characteristic
Antenna array type	L-shaped array
Number of antennas (M)	7
Antenna type	Isotropic
No. of receivers	3
No. of transmitters	1
No. of transmitter's locations	500
Distance between antennas (d)	$\lambda/2$
Channel model	Ray-Tracing + AWGN
Frequency scaling multipliers	$2M, M, M/2$
No. of active subcarriers	56, 28, 14
SNR (dB)	5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30

Fig. 20 presents a high-level overview of the experiment conducted in MATLAB, while Table IV lists the simulation parameters. The transmitter generates a single passband OFDM signal adhering to the DECT 2020 NR waveform (refer to Table III). This signal passes through a ray tracing channel and undergoes AWGN to simulate a multipath and time-invariant channel in a virtual room, where a dominant LOS component is present.

Three receivers, positioned at different locations within this room, capture the signal using a seven-element uniform L-shaped array, created with the phased array system toolbox. The RF switch operates at a frequency of $f_r/2$, in which f_r can be $2Mf_s$, Mf_s , or $Mf_s/2$. We define $2M$, M , and $M/2$ as frequency scaling multipliers (FSMs) of f_s . Additionally, to adhere to the Nyquist–Shannon sampling theorem, the active subcarrier counts are 56, 28, and 14 for $2M$, M , and $M/2$ FSMs, respectively.

The receivers process the array frequency response and estimate the DOA using Algorithm 1, subsequently transmitting these DOA estimates to the cloud. The cloud, in turn, calculates the transmitter's position using the BFGS method to find the MinSE (see Section IV-B).

More specifically, in our experiments, we use a 3-D computer-aided design software to digitally create a furniture-filled room measuring $300 \times 200 \text{ m}^2$ as shown in Fig. 21. We use this virtual environment to apply the MATLAB's ray-tracing channel model, which utilizes the shooting and bouncing rays method with default parameters. For further details, refer to [54].

Within the virtual room, we position three receivers to form the vertices of an equilateral triangle in the xy -plane. The Cartesian coordinates of the three receivers, in meters, are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r}_1^T &= [0, -70, 40] \\ \mathbf{r}_2^T &= [70, 0, 35.0] \\ \mathbf{r}_3^T &= [-25.62, 95.62, 30]. \end{aligned}$$

We position the transmitter at 500 unique locations, ensuring LOS alignment with all three receivers. These locations are

Fig. 20. Illustrative overview of the experiment.

distributed across four circles, with each circle having 125 positions. In the xy -plane, these circles are concentric and their centers coincide with the centroid of the equilateral triangle formed by the receivers. Each circle has a unique height (z coordinate) and radius. Fig. 22 provides a top-down view of the transmitter, receivers, concentric circles, and the equilateral triangle.

More precisely, we position the transmitter according to the following equation:

$$\mathbf{p}_{i,\alpha} = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 + a_i R \cos\left(\frac{2\pi\alpha}{125}\right) \\ c_2 + a_i R \sin\left(\frac{2\pi\alpha}{125}\right) \\ 60 + b_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{meters}) \quad (71)$$

in which $a_i = 2^{-i+1}$, $b_i = 5(i+1)$, $\alpha = 0, 1, \dots, 124$, and $R = 64 \text{ m}$. The index $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$ identifies the circles and

$$\begin{bmatrix} c_1 \\ c_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 35 - \frac{35\sqrt{3}}{3} \\ -35 + \frac{35\sqrt{3}}{3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{meters})$$

represents the centroid's x and y coordinates of the mentioned equilateral triangle.

Note that, we explicitly define the positions of the transmitter instead of placing it randomly for two reasons. First, random placement would not guarantee LOS alignment with all three receivers. Second, defining explicitly the transmitter's position improves the reproducibility of our research.

A. Measurement Description

We use box plots to visualize each FSM's angular error statistics (mean in black). Each plot summarizes 1500 angular

Fig. 21. Illustration of the $300 \times 200 \text{ m}^2$ digitally constructed room composed of out-of-scale furniture. Blue icons represent receivers equipped with uniform L-shaped arrays, while the red one denotes the transmitter.

Fig. 22. Top view (xy -plane) of the digital room. The fixed receivers (blue icons) form an equilateral triangle while the transmitter is placed in different positions around concentric circles.

errors (three receivers \times 500 locations) per SNR level. From Analytic Geometry, we define the angular error between two vectors (DOA) as

$$\Delta d_{i,\alpha,k} \triangleq \arccos \left(\frac{\mathbf{d}_{i,\alpha,k}^T \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{i,\alpha,k}}{\|\mathbf{d}_{i,\alpha,k}\| \|\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{i,\alpha,k}\|} \right) \quad (72)$$

where $\mathbf{d}_{i,\alpha,k}$ signifies the actual DOA from receiver r_k , $k = 1, 2, \text{ or } 3$, to the transmitter at location $\mathbf{p}_{i,\alpha}$, and $\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{i,\alpha,k}$ is its estimation via the DOA method (see Fig. 23). Note that, $\mathbf{d}_{i,\alpha,k}$ follows the same structure as defined in (67), with added indices i, α to identify the transmitter's location among the 500 options.

Fig. 23. Illustration of the angular error defined in (72).

Similarly, we use box plots with means (in black) for position errors. Each plot summarizes 500 position errors per SNR levels. The position error is given by

$$\Delta \mathbf{p}_{i,\alpha} \triangleq \|\mathbf{p}_{i,\alpha} - \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{i,\alpha}\| \quad (73)$$

where $\mathbf{p}_{i,\alpha}$ represents the actual transmitter's position, while $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{i,\alpha}$ denotes the estimated position by the positioning method.

B. Results and Discussions

Table V shows instances where the DOA method failed to estimate elevation angles. We attribute these failures primarily to the TLS estimation technique applied to v_1 and μ_1 . This technique, like any other estimation approach, is susceptible to errors, particularly under conditions of low SNRs and limited data, as in the case of $M/2$ FSM at 5 dB SNR.

Consequently, the complex number ψ_1 , computed from the estimates \hat{v}_1 and $\hat{\mu}_1$ in (66), falls outside the range of $[-1, 1]$. This range is essential as it determines the valid input domain for the $\arccos(\bullet)$ function in (65), which is constrained to output angles between $[0^\circ, 90^\circ]$. When the input exceeds this range, the function outputs complex numbers, rendering results meaningless for our application.

1) *Angular Error Statistics:* Fig. 24(a)–(c) illustrates the angular metrics of the DOA method with FSMs of $M/2$, M , and $2M$, respectively. For clarity in visualization, we have excluded from figures extreme outliers that exceed 11° error. Each graph reveals the mean curve positioned slightly above the median value, attributable to the mean's higher

Fig. 24. (a)–(c) Illustrate the angular metrics of the DOA method for different FSMs. (d)–(f) Display the position metrics of the positioning method for the same FSM values. For uniformity and clarity, all graphs are truncated at 11° and 11 m.

TABLE V
NUMBER OF DOA ESTIMATION FAILURES PER 1500 ESTIMATES

FSM	SNR (dB)						
	5	10	15	20	25	30	
2M		21	5	3	2	1	1
M		33	5	4	2	2	3
M/2		129	11	8	5	1	3

susceptibility to extreme outliers compared to other statistical measures, pushing the mean above the median.

The DOA method faces significant challenges under low SNR conditions, as shown by the broad error distribution at 5 dB SNR across all three FSMs. This is reflected in the wide interquartile range and the presence of numerous outliers,

underscoring the difficulty of accurately estimating DOA in noisy environments.

The DOA method exhibits the highest angular error at an FSM of $M/2$, which may indicate the impact of reduced sample count on accuracy. In contrast, the method shows nearly identical angular metrics at M and $2M$ FSMs, except at an SNR of 5 dB. This similarity suggests that the DOA method can maintain comparable accuracy at FSMs between $2M$ and M , provided the bandwidth of active subcarriers decreases proportionally. Additionally, at M and $2M$ FSMs, over 50% of the data achieves a subdegree error starting from an SNR of 10 dB, increasing to over 75% at an SNR of 20 dB.

2) *Positional Error Statistics*: Fig. 24(d)–(f) displays positional metrics for the positioning method at FSMs of $M/2$, M , and $2M$. We exclude outliers exceeding 11 m error for better visual clarity. Here, each graph shows a mean curve

Fig. 25. Position estimates. Although the method estimates 3-D locations, only their 2-D projections on the xy plane are shown for clarity. (a) $M/2$ FSM at 10-dB SNR. (b) $2M$ FSM at 30-dB SNR.

significantly above the median, underlining the impact of extreme outliers more than in the angular error statistics.

These outliers mainly originate from two issues. First, the position estimator might converge on a value far from the actual position, despite accurate angle estimates. This issue arises from the potential nonconvex nature of the optimization problem in (70), where nonlinear optimization may fail to identify the global minimum (the actual position). Second, poor angle estimations by the DOA method also contribute to outliers.

Notably, the poor DOA estimates at 5 dB SNR for $M/2$ FSM lead to significantly large position errors, rendering the positioning method unreliable under these conditions. The magnitude of these errors is so substantial that, in Fig. 24(d), the boxplot is truncated at 11 m to maintain uniformity with the other figures and visual clarity.

A small increase in the average value is observed from an SNR of 25 to 30 dB, suggesting a higher incidence of outliers at 30 dB. However, at 30 dB, the median, standard deviation, and the lower and upper quartiles reach their lowest values. This highlights the importance of considering multiple statistical metrics, rather than relying solely on the mean, due to its sensitivity to extreme values.

Given the DOA method's highest angular error at $M/2$ FSM, corresponding poor position metrics are expected. In contrast, position metrics at M and $2M$ FSMs are similar, with a slight advantage at $2M$. In both cases, over 50% of the data achieves a submeter position error from 15 dB SNR, increasing to nearly 75% from 25 dB SNR.

Fig. 25(a) and (b) illustrates two examples of the estimated locations on the xy plane using the positioning method. In Fig. 25(a), the estimates at 10 dB SNR for $M/2$ FSM exhibit clearly distorted circles. In contrast, Fig. 25(b) shows the best-case scenario at 30 dB SNR for $2M$ FSM, where the estimated positions closely resemble concentric circles.

VI. EMBEDDED SOFTWARE EXPERIMENTS

The experiment has two primary objectives. First, it evaluates the feasibility of using the DOA method in low-cost,

Fig. 26. Illustrative overview of the experiments in an nRF52480 SoC.

Fig. 27. Illustrative hardware designs for baseband operations in which $M = 7$.

low-power system-on-chips (SoC) for massive IoT networks. Second, it assesses the performance of digital baseband processing as peripherals to the SoC in a simulated hardware.

We implement the DOA method (Algorithm 1) directly onto an nRF52480 development kit (DK), without any operating systems or software layers. This bare-metal approach enables

Fig. 28. Illustration of a partially NLOS scenario: Receivers r_2 and r_3 estimate the DOAs based on the strongest reflected paths, \hat{l}_2 and \hat{l}_3 , respectively. These estimates differ significantly from the direct paths, l_2 and l_3 , leading to inaccuracies in the positioning method.

TABLE VI
DECT 2020 NR SOC FEATURES

SoC	Processor	Flash Memory	RAM	Supply Voltage
nRF9160 [55]	ARM Cortex M33 64 MHz	1 MB	256 KB	3.0-5V
nRF9161 [56]				
nRF9131 [57]				

TABLE VII
SOC IMPLEMENTATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Characteristic
Programming Language	C99
Compiler Optimization	-O1
Device	nRF52840 DK
Real-time Operating System	None
Floating-Point Format	Single Precision (FP32)

precise measurements of the algorithm's energy consumption, execution time, and memory footprint. The nRF52480 SoC, optimized for low-power IoT devices in massive IoT networks, incorporates a 64 MHz Arm Cortex-M4. Despite not supporting DECT 2020 NR, its computational capabilities are akin to nRF91 series devices that do. Table IV presents the primary characteristics of the nRF91 series.

We implement Algorithm 1 using the C99 programming language with single-precision floating-point (FP32) operations, aligning with the Arm Cortex-M4's FP32-only floating-point unit support. Table VII provides the implementation parameters. We measure RAM and Flash consumption using the `arm-none-eabi-size.exe` command from the Arm cross compiler toolchain.

We use the Otii Arc power tool connected to the nRF52840 DK for accurate energy measurement. We measure the execution time with the Saleae logic analyzer. For both measurements, we utilize a general-purpose input/output (GPIO)

port: set high at execution start and low at finish. This enables accurate measurement but may slightly overestimate energy usage due to GPIO activation. Fig. 26 provides an illustrative overview of the experiments in an nRF52480 SoC.

We develop both software and hardware versions of the digital baseband processing (see Fig. 15). In both cases, we consider an array with seven elements to match the number of antennas in simulation experiments (Section V). We implement the software version on the nRF52480 employing a fast Fourier transform (FFT) as the DFT algorithm. The hardware version targets a field programmable gate array (FPGA), simulating a potential DFT IC peripheral for the nRF91 SoCs. This peripheral also integrates an SPC and successive approximation 12-bit ADC, consistent with the ADC standards of the nRF52 and nRF91 series.

Written in C++, the hardware version is synthesized with AMD Vitis HLS and Vivado (version 2023.2) targeting a Zynq UltraScale+ xck26-sfvc784-2LV-c device at 64 MHz (matching nRF91's clock). It incorporates AXI-Stream (ARM native bus architecture) and the AMD FFT IP library [58] to design the DFT block.

We implement two hardware designs (see Fig. 27) as follows.

- 1) *High-Area, Low-Latency (V1)*: Employs seven parallel DFT cores for faster processing.
- 2) *Low-Area, High-Latency (V2)*: Uses a single DFT core, requiring sequential computation of antenna frequency responses.

A. Results

Table VIII presents the energy consumption, execution time, and memory footprint for Algorithm 1. Halving and quartering the FSM at 2M reduce execution time to roughly 43% and 66%, respectively, with similar energy reductions. However, the memory footprint exhibits subtle changes. This is because the algorithm code (stored in flash) remains the same, while variable data (stored in RAM) varies slightly with different sample rates.

Coin batteries in IoT devices typically range from 1 to 2000 mAh.¹ Considering only the DOA method's energy consumption and a 3V power supply, the nRF52840 can execute Algorithm 1 from around 199 000 (worst case) to 1 billion (best case) times. Notably, the worst case denotes an nRF52840 with an 1 mAh coin-battery running Algorithm 1 at 2M FSM. The best case designates the same device with a 2000 mAh coin-battery running Algorithm 1 at $M/2$ FSM.

The results for memory footprint, energy consumption, and execution time demonstrate that the DOA solution is well-suited for battery-powered devices in the nRF591 series.

Table IX shows that hardware implementations outperform the software counterpart by around 100 times. V1 is about three times faster than V2 due to its parallel DFT cores. However, Algorithm 1 is the bottleneck of the DOA estimation as it takes 2.26–0.76 ms to execute. This

¹According to Mouser Electronics, see: <https://www.mouser.com/c/power/batteries/coin-cell-battery>.

TABLE VIII
PERFORMANCE PARAMETERS OF ALGORITHM 1 PER FSM

FSM	Energy Usage (nWh)	Execution Time (ms)	RAM (kB)	Flash Memory (kB)
2M	15.1	2.26	6.45	16.7
M	8.02	1.24	4.45	16.7
M/2	5.08	0.76	3.45	16.7

TABLE IX
EXECUTION TIME OF BASEBAND OPERATIONS IN SOFTWARE AND HARDWARE PER FSM

FSM	Software	Execution Time (ms) Hardware V1	Hardware V2
2M	1.44	2.09e−2	6.12e−2
M	0.70	1.09e−2	3.33e−2
M/2	0.36	5.89e−3	1.94e−2

TABLE X
RESOURCE UTILIZATION OF BASEBAND OPERATIONS

Design	FSM	LUTs	FFs	DSPs	BRAMs
V1	2M	6169	10411	21	14
	M	5841	10191	21	14
	M/2	5472	9642	21	14
V2	2M	1428	1912	3	2
	M	1246	1876	3	2
	M/2	1171	1797	3	2

makes the performance difference between **V1** and **V2** negligible.

Table X presents the resource utilization of the hardware implementations: finite-state machine (FSMs), digital signal processing (DSP) blocks, block RAMs (BRAMs), look-up tables (LUTs), and flip-flops (FFs).

The significant difference in the usage of LUTs and FFs between **V1** and **V2** suggests that **V2** would be much less burdensome on the SoC's resources. Lower LUT and FF usage translates to less logic and state storage needed, which is beneficial for minimizing the silicon footprint and potentially reducing the power consumption of the peripheral. Both configurations use a fixed number of DSPs and BRAMs, regardless of the FSM size. Since DSPs and BRAMs are critical for performance but also costly in terms of area and power, the minimal usage in **V2** (only three DSPs and two BRAMs) is advantageous for integration into SoCs.

In summary, the **V2** design, with its resource efficiency and negligible latency increase, is better suited for SoC peripherals.

VII. LIMITATIONS

This research does not compare Algorithm 1 with other methods because, to the best of the authors' knowledge, there are no existing publications on the implementation of a 5G DOA method for array sequential sampling at the bare-metal level in an SoC. Notably, we found that most array signal processing implementations are typically conducted on desktop platforms using high-level programming languages

composed of numerical computing tools, such as MATLAB or Python. This approach contrasts significantly with the bare-metal firmware development on an SoC undertaken in this research, which enables precise measurement of memory footprint, energy consumption, and execution time.

The implemented DOA method does not account for hardware imperfections at the receiver. These imperfections can arise from ADC resolution, sampling jitter, antenna radiation pattern variations within the array, and any RF circuitry that introduces phase shifts to the received signal. To address this, it would be crucial to integrate that the DOA method with an array calibration technique for real-world antenna arrays to mitigate these imperfections.

BFGS provides a good starting point, but implementing more elaborate optimization methods can significantly enhance position estimation. For instance, including the indoor environment's size constraints in the positioning model would require a constraint optimization algorithm. This algorithm would leverage these size limitations to refine estimations. Generally, considering more information allows tailor-made development of optimization algorithms, potentially increasing the position accuracy.

In typical indoor environments, the transmitter may not have a direct LOS to all three receivers. In partial NLOS scenarios, the direct path signal may be weaker than its multipath components. The implemented indoor positioning solution will estimate the array response based on the strongest reflected signal, which may have a completely different DOA than its direct path counterpart, as shown in Fig. 28. As a result, the accuracy of the positioning method can be significantly compromised. We consider two potential solutions to mitigate this issue.

One approach involves strategically placing more than three anchor nodes throughout the indoor setting, such as on the ceiling, to enhance LOS coverage. By increasing the number of anchor nodes, we can improve the likelihood that at least some of the receivers will have a direct LOS to the transmitter. This would allow the positioning method to utilize multiple DOA estimations, potentially improving its accuracy. Additionally, the system can identify NLOS anchor nodes and exclude their estimates, provided there are at least three LOS receivers. Some well-established studies on NLOS identification are available, such as those [59], [60], [61].

If the direct path signal is attenuated but not completely blocked, it will likely be the earliest TOA component. In this scenario, the receiver could estimate the array response based on the earliest TOA. However, this task is challenging, as the attenuated direct path signal could fall below the noise floor, making it difficult to detect, and stronger multipath components may overshadow it [62]. Furthermore, multipath signals could arrive very shortly after the direct path signal, complicating the distinction between them. Even if the direct path signal is detected, its direction may be significantly shifted due to refraction as it passes through the obstructing material [63]. Moreover, this approach demands high clock synchronization between receivers and transmitters [14], which adds complexity and cost to the positioning solution.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This work investigated a potential affordable, energy-efficient DOA-based localization solution for DECT 2020 NR, a new standard for massive IoT networks without native positioning. Our solution proposed receivers with L-shaped antenna arrays and a single RF chain. Each antenna samples the OFDM signal sequentially via an RF switch, with the signal time divided into sample and switch slots. We found that the slot rate should be at least $2Mf_s$ to avoid aliasing. Additionally, we introduced a novel and simple DOA method optimized for OFDM signals featuring a dominant LOS component and sequential sampling. Simulations and experiments on a low-cost, resource-constrained nRF52480 SoC validated the solutions.

The simulated indoor localization scenario involved receivers estimating DOAs with a cloud service leveraging these estimates for positioning. The experiment simulated a furnished room with noise and a multipath channel using AWGN and a ray-tracing channel model. Results confirmed the effectiveness of the DOA method. With a slot rate of $2Mf_s$ and a 15 dB SNR, over 50% of angular estimates achieved subdegree angular accuracy, increasing to 75% at 20 dB. Over 50% of position estimates fell below the submeter error at 15 dB SNR onward, reaching nearly 75% from 25 dB SNR. Furthermore, halving the slot rate showed minimal impact on accuracy, provided active subcarriers were proportionally reduced. This is significant, potentially enabling cheaper ADCs and increased energy savings for anchor nodes.

Embedded software experiments on the nRF52480 SoC confirmed the practical feasibility of the DOA method for IoT devices under consideration. We evaluated memory footprint, energy consumption, and execution time. Additionally, we implemented the FFT block in software and also in hardware (FPGA). The hardware simulated one-core and multicore DFT peripherals for the SoC. Results indicated that a single-core DFT peripheral offered the most cost-effective solution with a negligible execution time overhead compared to the DOA estimation time.

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